

CATEGORIES OF ANALOGIES IN THE EPIC OF "FARHAD AND SHIRIN"

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Abstract: *This article discusses the types of similes used in Navoi's work. Analyzes of concrete and abstract, traditional and individual similes are presented. In Navoi's work, similes are formed with the help of three different grammatical devices and information is provided about their unequal possibilities in forming simile devices.*

Keywords: *Symbol of simile, basis of simile, extended simile, concrete simile, abstract simile, traditional simile, individual simile.*

Similes are divided into several groups according to the basis of their occurrence, their use in the language of artistic literature, their meanings, and the composition of their components. All analogies arise through intuition and imagination. In this regard, similes are divided into two large groups.

The first group of similes is based on sensations and real objects and events are compared. Such similes are conventionally called concrete similes. Since concrete analogies are based on sensations, it is possible to believe that such an analogy exists in nature. That is, a person's mind can believe¹.

Concrete similes arise on the basis of one of the sensory organs of sight, hearing, smell, taste and skin.

1. Analogies caused by the organ of vision:

Alarg'a oshkoro-yu nihoni, Ko'z ichra ashkdek asratqil oni (FSh).

2. Analogies created through the organ of hearing:

Choparda quyrug'in aylab alam ul, Qulog'idek ayog'din-bosh qalam ul (FSh)².

3. Analogies created through the sense of smell:

Dimog'ida burunkim quvvat erdi, Tanida dog'i zoru sihat erdi (FSh).

4. Similes related to taste:

Tuzub bazm ul kecha ham komu nokom, Ichib achchiqqa-chchIQ bir necha jom (FSh).

¹ Mukarramov M. Simile in Uzbek. –Tashkent: Science, 1976. –P. 25.

² A.Navoiy. Farhod va Shirin. – Toshkent: G'afur G'ulom, 2020. – B. 23-40.

5. Analogies related to the skin sense organ:

Ichinda sham o'tluq joni ma'yus, Teri birla so'ngok andoqki fonus (FSh).

The second group of similes emerges on the basis of imagination. Such analogies are conventionally called abstract analogies. **Abstract similes** occur in a person's eyes, imagination, or imagination. In fact, such analogies do not exist in things and events in nature. In these, fantasy and exaggeration prevail. Abstract similes are often expressed by the words seem, turn, remind, as if, be, as³.

a) by "go'yo" word:

Bu yon go'yoki surmishdur takovarki, gardidin ko'runmas mehri xovar (FSh).

b) by "bo'lub" word:

Bo'lub zoyil taarruz ehtimoli, Oyog'i sustayib, sa'b o'ldi holi (FSh).

c) By "bo'yla" word:

Urub yuzga nadomat ashkidin suv, Magar ketgay ko'zungdin bo'yla uyqu (FSh).

It seems that in the above abstract similes, things and events are not realistically compared to each other. Exaggeration and fantasy prevail in them.

In general, concrete similes are based on feelings and are distinguished by their truthfulness, reality, and vitality. Since they often combine some characteristic of the depicted image, they have strong imagery, emotional expressiveness. In abstract similes, the general characteristics of things and events are compared based on exaggeration in the imagination of a person, but in reality there is no such similarity between things and events.

Similes in the language of fiction are divided into two groups according to their use: **1) traditional (traditional) similes; 2) individual similes**⁴.

1. Traditional similes are similes in the spoken speech of the people, which are included in the language of the artistic work without being changed by the writer. The features of effectiveness and concreteness are not clearly embodied in them. Such similes have lost their figurative and emotional-expressive features by being used in everyday speech.

³ Mukarramov M. Simile in Uzbek. –Tashkent: Science, 1976. –P. 27

⁴ Mukarramov M. Simile in Uzbek. –Tashkent: Science, 1976. –P. 25-27.

A.F. Yefremov paid attention to this in his article on the study of similes in the language of artistic works, and called the similes used in the live speech of the Russian language with the term "stereotype similes"⁵. *Yuzi ul mujdadin guldek ochildi, Qo'pub mehmonsarog'a azm qildi (FSh)*.

2. Individual similes are similes used by the writer's skillful use of vernacular language. Emotional expressiveness and figurativeness are clearly visible in them. In the language of a work of art, such similes are often given through the author's speech and are distinguished by their originality, concreteness, and lack of imagination of the reader.

In general, in individual similes there is a strong emotion in the specific image, which is associated with imagery and emotionality. Individual similes are realized by the writer's careful examination of real life facts, and the lightless, dark, abstract aspects of the described object are realized and clarified in the imagination of the reader: *Qoshim mehrobini yod aylagan dam, Yangi oydek bo'lurmu qomating xamg' (FSh)*.

In conclusion, it can be said that similes used in the literary language differ in their positive and negative meanings. Similes with a positive meaning are given in the portrait, character of positive characters in the work of art. An important sign and feature of them is compared to the positive sign and feature of the moon, sun, fruit trees and other things. Negative characters are compared to harmful, unpleasant things in life. The objects of comparison play an important role in the positive and negative meaning of similes.

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